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АНАЛИЗ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ СКРИНИНГА РАКА МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ В Г. ГРОДНО РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ

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Аннотация: Проведен анализ результатов проведения скрининга рака молочной железы на ранних стадиях путем выполнения программ организации маммографического скрининга с максимальным охватом женского населения Ленинского и Октябрьского районов г. Гродно Республики Беларусь. Анализ полученных результатов свидетельствует о том, что при проведении маммографического скрининга в период с 2016 по 2019 гг. рак молочной железы был выявлен у 0,7 % женщин. На доклинической стадии (0-1) рак молочной железы диагностирован у 43,0 % обследованных пациенток, когда он не определялся ни пациенткой при самообследовании, ни врачом при осмотре и пальпации молочных желез, что свидетельствует о целесообразности проведения маммографического исследования для эффективной диагностики скрытых форм рака.

Ключевые слова: рак молочной железы, маммография, скрининг, самообследование

THE ANALYSIS OF RESULTS OF CARRYING OUT SCREENING OF THE BREAST CANCER IN GRODNO OF REPUBLIC OF BELARUS

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Annotation: The analysis of results of carrying out screening of a breast cancer at early stages by implementation of programs of the organization of mammography screening with the maximum coverage of female population of Lenin and October districts of Grodno of Republic of Belarus is carried out. The analysis of the received results demonstrates that when carrying out mammography screening during the period from 2016 to 2019 the breast cancer was revealed at 0.7 % of women. At a preclinical stage (0-I) the breast cancer is diagnosed for 43.0 % of the examined patients when it was not defined neither by the patient at self-inspection, nor the doctor at survey and a palpation of mammary glands that demonstrates expediency of carrying out a mammography research for effective diagnostics of the latent forms of cancer.

Keywords: breast cancer, mammography, screening, self-inspection

Relevance. The breast cancer takes the second place in structure of oncological incidence at female population in Republic of Belarus (17.6 %) and the first place in structure of mortality of women from malignant new growths (16.9 %). The indicator of cancer cases of a mammary gland during 2011-2017 was 82.25 cases on 100000 population (from 76.7 in 2011 up to 87.8 cases on 100000 women in 2017). At 3-10 % of patients with this pathology development of a disease is connected with availability of mutations in genes of BRCA1, BRCA2, CHECK, NBS1, tP53. Breast cancer arises as result of active uncontrollable division of atypical cancer cells. This pathology can develop against the background of pretumor diseases to which the mastopathy and fibroadenomas belongs [1, 2].

Early detection of malignant new growths is possible in case of implementation of effective programs of the organization of screening which main objective – to find cancer before its clinical implication when it has local character and can be cured.

Mammography screening is proved, proved and necessary for implementation of early diagnostics of not palpated forms of a breast cancer.

Purpose. The analysis of results of carrying out screening of a breast cancer at early stages by implementation of programs of the organization of mammography screening with the maximum coverage of female population of Lenin and October districts of Grodno of Republic of Belarus.

Materials and methods of a research. Screening mammography was carried out on stationary mammographs – "Giotto" ("I.M.S.", Italy) with the CR system of digitization of the x-ray image, "MELODY-B" ("V.M.S.", Italy) and "Mammoskan" ("Adani", Belarus) with stereotaxic prefixes for carrying out additional examination (an aim needle biopsy of not palpated educations).

Invited almost healthy women aged from 50 till 69 years old relating to a zone of service of policlinics No. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, the 7th Grodno to screening mammography inspection. The women having serious associated diseases, which with high probability would lead to death in the next years or a breast, cancer in the anamnesis did not enter into the contingent, which is subject to screening.

At the direction on screening mammography patients were given for acquaintance specially developed instructions for participating in screening of a breast cancer, containing necessary information on mammography screening, preparation for a research, requirements imposed before its carrying out and actions after obtaining result of a research.

Interpretation of results was carried out by two radiologists independently of each other according to the BI-RADS system and respect for the international criteria of quality.

In the course of implementation of the program of screening of a breast cancer daily quality control of mammograms with the special phantom was carried out, also 2 times a year radiologists carried out assessment of quality of work of X-ray laboratory assistants, for the purpose of reduction of amount of false positive and false-negative results of a X-ray mammography analysis and saving information, important for diagnostics.

The obtained data were processed by a set of standard statistical programs.

Results and their discussion. 10392 women were subject to mammography screening in 2016. It is surveyed 9951 (95.7 % of quantity of subjects). 80 cases of a breast cancer are revealed, the identification percent from quantity of surveyed made 0.8. In 0–I stages of a disease 36 women (45 %) are revealed. In 2017 was subject to mammography screening of 7816 women. It is surveyed 7741 (99.0 % of quantity of subjects). 84 cases of a

breast cancer are revealed, the identification percent from quantity of surveyed made 1.08. In 0-I stages of a disease 32 women (38.1 %) are revealed. In 2018 was subject to mammography screening 8971 women. It is surveyed 8871 (99 % of quantity of subjects). 45 cases of a breast cancer are revealed, the identification percent from quantity of surveyed made 0.5. In 0-I stages of a disease it is revealed 21 women (46.6 %). In 2019 was subject to mammography screening of 7590 women. It is surveyed 7544 (99 % of quantity of subjects). 44 cases of a breast cancer are revealed, the identification percent from quantity of surveyed made 0.6. In 0-I stages of a disease 20 women (45.5 %) are revealed.

In four years according to the program of screening 34107 female residents of Grodno were examined. The breast cancer is revealed at 253 (0.74 %) patients.

Distribution of the revealed breast cancer on stages was the following: 0 stage – 4 (1.6 %), the I stage – 105 (41.4 %), the II stage – 114 (45.0 %) and the III stage – 25 (10.0 %), the IV stage – 5 (2.0 %).

Average age of women with the revealed malignancy was 58 years.

Conclusions.

The analysis of the received results demonstrates that when carrying out mammography screening during the period from 2016 to 2019 the breast cancer was revealed at 0.7 % of women.

At a preclinical stage (0-I) the breast cancer is diagnosed for 43.0 % of the examined patients when it was not defined neither by the patient at self-inspection, nor the doctor at survey and a palpation of mammary glands that demonstrates expediency of carrying out a mammography research for effective diagnostics of the latent forms of cancer.

Early diagnostics of this pathology promotes timely performance of organ-preserving operations and has high psychological value for women.

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